

Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Matthews et al. (2025)

A Database for Reclaimed Precast Concrete Elements

Introduction & Data Collection Guidelines

Abstract

This report introduces the framework and intended workflow to develop a database of precast concrete elements reclaimed from deconstructed buildings. The development of an open-source database of precast concrete components in the EU is part of work package 1 in the ReCreate project, which focuses on the digitalisation of precast elements. The database structure in the Data Collection stage is discussed in detail to provide guidance for gathering data on successfully reclaimed elements. The purpose of the data collection stage is to parametrically describe the geometric, longitudinal, and transverse reinforcement designs of a precast element, such that it can be remodelled into a digital twin capable of performing detailed structural analyses. Several example cases from the Dutch donor office complex 'Prinsenhof A' are provided to help illustrate the concepts introduced throughout the framework. Once collected, the data is stored within the open-source relational database management system, MySQL. During storage, the data structure is converted into an optimised format for future 3D modelling and BIM applications. The database also serves as a valuable platform to define architectural and life-cycle characteristics to provide a holistic overview of each reclaimed element.

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1. Introduction

The ReCreate project is a European consortium research undertaking, funded by the Horizon 2020 programme, aimed at giving precast concrete elements, initially intended for single use, an extended, “circular” life span in one or more new building structures. The goal is to assess and improve the technical feasibility of such a circular life cycle, considering element disassembly, quality control, design for reuse and reconstruction.

The project primarily involves the Netherlands, Germany, Finland, and Sweden. The consortium team includes one university from each country and various industrial partners working in the built environment. The project spans academic and industrial research and development, organised into ten work packages and four country clusters. Figure 1.1 below shows the work packages (WPI-WPI0) that comprise the project.

In parallel with the scientific research, each country cluster is to undertake a real-life pilot deconstruction/element-reuse project. The Dutch project involved the complete deconstruction of a nine-storey office building complex, “Prinsenhof A” in Arnhem. All structural concrete elements from this building have been disassembled, and most have been transported to Heerde, where they will be used to construct a new multi-storey mixed-use building in 2025/2026. For more information on the ReCreate project, please visit recreate-project.eu.

Figure 1.1. ReCreate work packages and their relations.

Work package 1 of the ReCreate project involves the analysis of precast concrete systems, emphasising mapping, taxonomy, and digital collection of precast concrete systems across the EU through open databases. To design new buildings and structures using reclaimed elements, it is first necessary to have an underlying database in which they are

readily available. Therefore, this report introduces the proposed framework for such a database and provides guidelines for **data collection** using prepared XLSX templates, tailored to each element type. Although the element database does not fall under any specific deliverable, it can serve as a cornerstone for task D1.4 (digitalisation of precast concrete elements) and prove particularly helpful across WP2 (Deconstruction), WP3 (Logistics and Processing), WP4 (Quality Management), and WP5 (Redesign and Reassembly). This report is intended to serve as a comprehensive guideline for collecting data related to element geometry, reinforcement, material properties, and site metadata. An accompanying journal paper is currently under production, which explores the downstream relational database architecture and implementations in greater detail.

Before narrowing the focus on the database structure, it is first essential to recognise the unique challenges of the intended pipeline as a whole. Counter to the typical design process, the database must work backwards from an existing precast element – with fixed geometric, design, and material properties – reverse engineering into a set of parametric variables that encapsulate the necessary structural and architectural details of the element. From there, the element data can be reengineered into 3D digital models, allowing the architects to design and the engineers to calculate. The digital modelling phase is covered in WP5, intended to promote concrete element reuse in construction projects, aid in the design process, and thereby contribute to a circular economy. For information regarding downstream modelling applications, refer to the accompanying journal article.

1. 1. Relational Databases and UML

Considering the object-oriented nature of digital design applications, a relational database is the most suitable option for storing the required data. A relational database is a type of database management system (RDBMS) that organises and stores data in a structured manner, using *tables* to represent and manage information. Each table consists of *rows* (records) and *columns* (properties, variables, or attributes). Each row represents a specific entity, while each column represents a particular attribute or property of that entity.

Unified Modelling Language (UML) is a widely used standard for visually conceptualising various types of systems. UML class diagrams are often used for documenting the structure of relational databases by considering each table in the database as a *class*. A class is an abstract concept that defines categories of objects, describing aspects such as what attributes they should have, what relations they should have to each other, and what uniquely represents an object. An attribute of an object can either be a simple data item, such as a string or integer, or another more complex object. An *object* is an instance of a class, with specific values assigned to each of its attributes and linked to other objects through the relationships defined by the class. Collections (e.g., lists) are another data structure prominent in object-oriented programming and relational databases. A class can have a collection of objects designated as an attribute of that class. These could include, for example, linking drawings of an element or other relevant files to their instances within the database.

Class hierarchy refers to the inter-relationship of classes through a mechanism such as inheritance. This relationship involves the definition of a so-called “parent” or “super-class” with one or more “children” or “sub-classes”. An object instance of a subclass is by definition also considered an instance of the super-class; however, the inverse is not necessarily true – an instance of the super-class is not necessarily an instance of a specific subclass, or the parent can exist without the child, whereas the child cannot exist without the parent.

UML class diagrams can be a helpful tool for illustrating the schema of a database structure and conveying conceptual ideas. A class diagram is implemented in an RDBMS through an Entity-Relationship (ER) diagram, sometimes referred to as an Enhanced-Entity Relationship (EER) diagram. It is worth noting that class diagrams are useful tools for visualising a database’s layout (schema), but they show classes, not objects. Additionally, the values or objects that make up the attributes (i.e., the rows of the tables) are not displayed. Hence, the diagram shows the schema by which data is organised and stored, but not the data itself. Class diagrams and EER diagrams share much of the same logic and features, effectively conveying the same ideas. Converting a class diagram to an EER diagram adjusts some of the functionality of the diagram such that it can be used to support an actual database structure in the management system. For this project, MySQL was selected as the RDBMS of choice due to its high functionality, strong ability to scale, simple user interface, and open-source nature to help promote further collaboration.

The primary distinction between a UML and an EER diagram lies in the inclusion of keys in the latter. For every class in an EER diagram, a primary key (PK) must be defined, uniquely identifying every stored record. Keying enables query searches of individual records in databases that can scale into millions of data entries. Common practice is to have an incrementing integer for a PK. However, unique strings of characters can also be used to identify each instance. Next, a foreign key (FK) is created every time a relationship between two tables is established. The FK links one attribute from the parent table to an attribute within the child table, enabling data-linking and cross-referencing between tables. The approach for selecting an FK depends on the type of relationship between tables, although FKs are typically placed in the child table. In an EER diagram, table-to-table relations are first defined as either an *identifying* or a *non-identifying relationship*. An identifying relationship exists between tables that share the same primary key. Therefore, a record in the child table depends on the existence of a record in the parent table. Hence, the foreign key linking the two tables should be treated as the primary key of the child table. A non-identifying relationship explains the opposite case when two tables have different primary keys, typically shown through the primary key of the ‘sub-table’ being an ordinary attribute of the parent table. Finally, the relative multiplicity must be defined – e.g. one-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-many.

2. Database Structure

2.1. Proposed Framework

The proposed framework for the database follows a top-down hierarchical structure, breaking each element into its constituent properties. The pipeline for creating such a database can be thought of in three stages: data collection, data storage, and digital modelling. Figure 2.1 illustrates the intended pipeline. Each stage requires custom approaches to optimise for efficiency and simplicity while still capturing all necessary information to ‘ReCreate’ a complete element. As for the database itself, Stage 1 (collection) is the primary focus of this report, whereas Stage 2 (storage) and Stage 3 (digital modelling) are discussed in detail in an upcoming scientific article (which will be linked when published).

Figure 2.1. Element database workflow.

In Stage 1, Microsoft Excel templates are prepared to manage data collection. For now, the data collection stage remains a manual process, extracting the required information from available drawings or testing information. Deliberately approaching this manually for pilot data curation was beneficial to cultivate a more complete and holistic understanding of the reuse chain before investing in more efficient automation. In the future, cloud-based input forms may be explored to make the collection process more efficient for the end user. The data format in this stage is currently tailored toward 2D orthographic mapping systems to make transferring information from drawings to spreadsheets more intuitive. Stage 2 involves storing the parametric data in the RDBMS MySQL. Once all available information is collected for a particular building, the completed spreadsheets can be processed through Python to adjust the coordinates and mapping conventions into standardised machine-readable 3D systems, optimising for future digital modelling applications. In general, both stages of the workflow follow the same hierarchical structure:

1. Element metadata and taxonomy

2. Material properties
3. Element geometrical properties
4. Longitudinal reinforcement design
5. Transverse reinforcement design

Figure 2.2 presents the UML class diagram representing the structure of the *Data Collection* stage. It shows a system of classes, including the names of their attributes and inter-relations. As discussed in Section 1.1, each class represents a *table* in the database. The attributes of each class, in turn, represent the table *columns*. The required data type trails each attribute. This data type is fixed, representing the format of each attribute that MySQL expects when storing the data. If the data is inserted as an incorrect data type, programmatic errors will prevent it from being stored until corrected. The four typical datatypes used during data collection are:

- Strings – sequences of characters with undefined lengths.
- Integers – whole numbers.
- Floats – fractional numbers, generally up to a precision of 7 decimal digits.
- Boolean – TRUE or FALSE.
- Vector – an array of two or more integers or floating points, e.g., (x, y) or (x, y, z).

Choosing between an integer and a floating-point number, in the context of this database, depends mainly on the level of accuracy with which measurements can be obtained. Often, floats are used as a safety net where a number could be fractional or not.

Briefly, the three different types of relationships used in the Figure 2.2 UML diagram include inheritance (white arrow), composition (black diamond), and aggregation (white diamond). Inheritance expresses the conventional hierarchical parent-and-child relationship where the child cannot exist without the parent. Composition explains the relationship between a whole and its parts, where the two cannot be separated. Aggregation explains the relationship between a whole and a part where the two can be treated separately. The numbers and symbols alongside each relationship define the table-to-table quantities mentioned in Section 1.1 (e.g. 0-to-1, 1-to-1, etc.).

The UML structure can be separated into a series of tables for each element type—walls, beams, columns, and slabs—shown by the bounding boxes in Figure 2.2. Walls include both external walls and internal loading-bearing walls. Slabs can be hollow-core floor slabs (HCS) or solid slabs (including foundations). Each series of tables begins by defining the geometrical properties of an element (voids, additional components, existing connections). The longitudinal reinforcement design can then be spatially defined relative to the existing geometry, followed by the transverse reinforcement design. In the central area of Figure 2.2, tables which can be described generically are placed to improve storage efficiency. These include corbel geometry, longitudinal reinforcement anchorage, and concrete and steel material properties. The yellow tables in the upper-left corner of Figure 2.2 represent the donor building metadata relating to the deconstruction site.

Figure 2.2. UML class diagram of database structure for Data Collection phase. Note that this figure is a vector graphic and **maintains quality while zooming** to enable browsing through tables.

3. Data Collection

The following sections outline the inputs for each table based on the accompanying XLSX templates, the data structure, and the expected formatting required throughout the data collection stage. Flexible and robust Cartesian mapping conventions were adopted to adaptively capture any irregular or complex designs that are often seen in precast systems. Spatially capturing the geometrical and reinforcement properties will allow the elements to be more effectively remodelled and utilised to their full capabilities in new structural designs. Specific examples of elements observed in the Dutch donor building Prinsenhof A (Figure 3.1) are presented throughout the report to illustrate how the mapping systems should be used. All distance-based measurements are required in millimetres.

Figure 3.1. Dutch donor project building Prinsenhof A BIM Model developed by Lagemaat B.V.

An important feature of EER diagrams is the clarification of *Null* vs. *Not Null* constraints. When building the database in MySQL, the schema requires a priori knowledge of whether an attribute can allow null (empty or missing) inputs or whether it is mandatory to include a value (Not Null). This distinction is built into the database framework. Hence, during the data collection stage, if the spreadsheet contains missing data that the RDBMS expects, loading errors will stop the data from being uploaded. The tables in the following sections include whether each attribute is optional or mandatory. If in doubt about how to format the spreadsheet templates, it may be helpful to refer back to the UML diagram in Figure 2.2 and Tables 3.1 to 3.10 for the required datatypes, constraints, and descriptions.

3. 1. Donor Building Data

The donor building data can be found in the yellow tables in the top left corner of Figure 2.2. The *Donor Building* and *Circularity Data* tables only require a single record (row) for each deconstruction project. This data includes location, age, taxonomy, size, and circularity information. Any additional information that seems useful can be included in the *Notes* attribute. Table 3.1 below summarises the expected information for the *Donor Building* and *Circularity Data* tables.

Table 3.1. Donor Building Metadata attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Building ID [string]	Not Null	A multi-faceted taxonomy system of descriptive acronyms based on Hernández et al. (2025) and Stenberg et al. (2025). Figure 3.2 illustrates example taxonomies, where more information can be found in the above resources.
Name [string]	Not Null	e.g. 'Prinsenhof A' – ideally treated as a unique identifier.
Building Type [string]	Not Null	e.g., office building, industrial building, etc. – based on the donor building function.
Coordinates [float]	Not Null	Latitude and longitude coordinates (not GPS).
Country [string]	Not Null	The country where the building was constructed.
City [string]	Not Null	City where the building was constructed.
Construction Year [year]	Not Null	Numerical integer of the construction year.
Deconstruction Year [year]	Not Null	Numerical integer of the deconstruction year.
Deconstruction Company [string]	Not Null	Name of the deconstruction company.
Consequence Class [string]	Null	CC based on Eurocode 1992-1-1. Optional in case it is initially unknown – can be later updated.
Exposure Class [string]	Null	XC based on Eurocode 1992-1-1. Optional in case it is initially unknown – can be later updated.
Total Floor Area [float]	Not Null	Total deconstructed floor area.
Number of Wings [int]	Not Null	If the donor building included sub-buildings. E.g. Prinsenhof had a high-rise, low-rise, and core component.
Number of Storeys [list of integers]	Not Null	Written as a vertical list of integers for each sub-building.
Number of Elements	Not Null	The number of elements by type that were deconstructed in sufficient condition for reuse. If they are not expected to be reused, do not count them here.
Notes [text]	Null	Any additional notes that might be useful to future designers (optional).

3. 2. Element Metadata

The metadata information for each element type is shown in the pink tables in Figure 2.2. Each element type has a dedicated table. However, the information is mainly consistent

across them. These tables include a record (row) for every individual element retrieved from deconstruction, which is in sufficient condition to be reused.

The metadata tables include a large amount of taxonomic information for each element. The *[Element] ID* attribute (e.g., *Wall ID*, *Beam ID*, etc.) is a facet-based classification system developed by Hernández et al. (2025) to serve as a unique, human-readable descriptor for each element. Drawing upon research mapping pan-European precast concrete systems by Stenberg et al. (2025), the *Building ID* (Fig. 3.2a and Table 3.1) and element-type IDs encode the primary facets (project, manufacturer, year, location), substituting “UNK” placeholders for any unknown facets. Although these taxonomies are not replacements for formal national or international classification systems, they should be embedded into the Common Data Environment (CDE) for the given project (ISO 19650-1, 2018; Dervishaj et al., 2023). Figure 3.2 illustrates the general conventions with examples from the Swedish donor building. More details on the different facets and acronyms can be found at Hernández et al. (2025). Table 3.2 summarises the expected information for the element metadata tables, with distinctions between any nuances related to the element type.

Figure 3.2. Example naming conventions for (a) building taxonomies and (b) element taxonomies.

Table 3.2. Element Metadata attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Element ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Wall ID, Beam ID, Column ID, or Slab ID based on Figure 3.2b.
Building ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Same as Table 3.1 and Fig. 3.2a.
Product ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique ID specified in the original construction that identifies the unique product geometry. To avoid repetition across projects and ensure uniqueness, include the building project number as a prefix, e.g. 5415_HG01.
Reinforcement ID [<i>string</i>]	Null	Unique ID specified in the original construction that identifies a unique reinforcement design. Allows null in case drawings are not available. Include the project number as above.
Element Type [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Wall Type = loading-bearing façade, internal wall, etc. Beam Type = rectangular, half-joint, T-beam, I-beam, etc. Column Type = rectangular, elliptical, headed, or I-section. Slab Type = hollow-core slab (HCS) or solid slab.

Wing [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Sub-building ID or name as described in Table 3.1.
Floor Number [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Floor number where the element was in the donor wing.
Orientation [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Only for walls: North, South, East, West facing.
Grid Position [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Element position based on original construction drawings.
Coating Layer [<i>Boolean</i>]	Null	Does the element have any surface protection (e.g., plaster)? “Active” for stored and available for reuse, “Pending” if under consideration for a new design, “Unavailable” if reused in a new structure.
Status [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	
Has Tests [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	Have any tests (material properties, degradation, durability, QA, etc.) been performed on the element?
Has Damage [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	Does the element exhibit any damage that needs to be repaired or removed before being installation-ready?
Intervention Class	Not Null	Class description of element condition (following QA): “Installation-Ready”, “Maintenance”, “Strengthening” .
Storage Lat/Long [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Latitude and longitude coordinates of the storage location (not GPS).
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Any additional notes that might be useful to future designers (optional).

3.3. Walls and Façade Elements

The following sections discuss the requirements for data collection from reclaimed wall elements. These mapping conventions can be applied to all element types, excluding hollow-core slabs, which have unique attributes. Since walls generally have the most complex geometries and reinforcement designs, load-bearing façades from the Prinsenhof donor building are used for visual examples.

3.3.1. Wall Geometry

Every unique wall geometry from a deconstruction project will have its geometry mapped and recorded here. There is no need to repeat this process for every element; only those with unique geometries that can be linked to the *Wall Element* table by the *Product ID* attribute (PK). The geometry considered in this table is for the **load-bearing component** only. If the additional outer sandwich layers, including the insulation layer, are kept for future designs, these geometries are stored in a connecting sub-table (Section 3.3.1.2). Table 3.3 summarises the expected information for the ‘*Wall Geometry*’ table.

The Cartesian coordinate system used to define the geometry of an element without being constrained to generic physical descriptors is illustrated in Figure 3.3. Figure 3.3 represents a typical façade geometry used in Prinsenhof (*Product ID: 5415_G01*). Following a traditional orthographic layout (front elevation, side cross-section, and plan view), the idea is to record the 2D coordinate position of every critical junction or discontinuity along the perimeter of the element. Standard CAD/BIM axis conventions are used for each view, shown in Figure 3.3, where *x* describes the global length, *z* is the global height, and *y* is the global thickness. Voids geometries are considered in a sub-table, so only the parent element geometry

needs to be mapped for this stage. The process for recording the wall geometry can be summarised as:

1. Using Western mathematical convention (**left to right, bottom to top**), identify the origin point (0, 0) in each orthographic view.
2. After identifying the origin, **move clockwise** around the perimeter of each view, recording the coordinates at each junction. If ever in doubt whether a point is necessary, think whether the overall geometry could be digitally remade if it were missing, and otherwise include it.
3. An optional radius/bevel component is included with every point to describe any junctions or corners containing curvature or small tapered edges. If no curve or bevel is present, insert $r = 0$.
4. List each new coordinate point vertically in the spreadsheet to create a list. The coordinates can either be stored as integers or floats, depending on the level of accuracy available.
5. Repeat for the next unique wall geometry.

Table 3.3. Wall Geometry attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 3.2.
Reinforcement ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 3.2.
Mirrored Design? [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	A precast wall with identical geometry may be reflected about an axis to fit in a different position in the donor building – e.g. a corner or boundary element.
Count [<i>integer</i>]	Not Null	Number of elements sharing this geometry [Product ID], which are defined in Table 3.2.
Front View Coordinates [<i>list of points (x,z,r)</i>]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the front elevation of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Side View Coordinates [<i>list of points (y,z,r)</i>]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the cross-sectional view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Plan View Coordinates [<i>list of points (x,y,r)</i>]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the plan view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Sandwich Panels [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	A Boolean indicating whether any additional (non-structural) panels are left attached to the load-bearing component.
Concrete Strength Class [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Concrete class based on original design specifications.
Max Aggregate Size [<i>int</i>]	Null	Maximum aggregate used in concrete mixture (optional).
Concrete Type [<i>string</i>]	Null	Type of concrete mix to determine density. Options may include: “Normal” , “Lightweight” , “Insulating ultralight” , “UHPC” , “Heavyweight” , “Pervious” .

Notes [text]

Null

Additional technical notes that might be of use to future designers. It can include any details not captured by the attributes.

Figure 3.3. Geometric design of facade element G01 from Prinsenhof A. Some details differ from the actual element for presentation purposes.

3.3.1.1. Wall Voids

The number of voids in a wall element typically determines the reinforcement design and specific reference system used to map the reinforcement. In a general sense, voids are defined as any recess bounded by at least three sides within the governing geometry. Hence, windows and doors are considered voids, whereas overhangs/cantilevers are deemed part of the overall geometry (similar for corbels, but these are treated as separate entities). Voids are linked to the global geometry through the *Product ID* attribute, which functions as a primary and foreign key.

The 3D coordinates (x, z, y) are recorded for every void corner throughout the thickness of the element. Any non-uniformity through the parent thickness or pitching is captured within the list of coordinates. The terminology for the different areas of a wall element is described in Section 3.3.2. Each point is vertically listed in the spreadsheet, similar to the geometry coordinates in Section 3.3.1.

If there are no voids in the wall system, record a zero under the *Void Count* attribute and leave the other attributes empty – this will supersede the Not Null constraints for the other attributes. Table 3.4 summarises the expected information for the *Wall Voids* table.

Table 3.4. Wall Voids table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Void Count [int]	Not Null	The number of voids within a geometry.
Void Coordinates [list of points (x, z, y)]	Not Null	The 3D coordinates at each corner or geometric change written as a vertical list.

3.3.1.2. Additional Panelling

If any of the original sandwich panels are kept intact with the load-bearing component for use in future designs, the geometry can be mapped in this sub-table. These may include outer façade panels, exterior design finishes, insulation layers, or any other layer not contributing to the structural resistance of the principal wall element.

Table 3.5 treats the mapping for insulation layers and other panel types separately. This arrangement allows for slightly more freedom when mapping panels with irregular geometries, such as outer cladding, aesthetic layers or exterior architectural panels, while maintaining simplicity with insulation. Similar to Table 3.3, an optional radius or bevel component can be added to each coordinate point to describe curved, rounded, or tapered edges. If none are present, insert zero or leave blank. The external finishing and design parameters in Table 3.5 are currently optional placeholders which will be explored in more detail in future versions.

Table 3.5. Additional Panelling table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [string]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 3.2.
Has Void [Boolean]	Not Null	A Boolean for whether the panels have voids or not.

Panel Front Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (x, z, r)]	Null	Lists of coordinates as described in Section 3.3.1, based on the front elevation of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes. Use the same origin point as Table 3.3.
Panel Side Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (y, z, r)]	Null	Lists of coordinates as described in Section 3.3.1, based on the cross-sectional view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes. Use the same origin point as Table 3.3.
Panel Plan Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (x, y, r)]	Null	Lists of coordinates as described in Section 3.3.1, based on the plan view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes. Use the same reference origin point as Table 3.3.
Panel Design Finish [<i>string</i>]	Null	An optional aesthetic description of the panel finish, which may include terms such as smooth, textured, rough, etc.
Insul. Front Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (x, z)]	Null	List of coordinates for the front view of the insulation layer. Use the same reference origin as Table 3.3.
Insul. Side Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (y, z)]	Null	List of coordinates for the side view of the insulation layer. Use the same reference origin as Table 3.3.
Insul. Plan Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (x, y)]	Null	List of coordinates for the plan view of the insulation layer. Use the same reference origin as Table 3.3.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

When mapping the coordinates of extra panels, it is crucial to **use the same local origin as defined in the primary geometry** in Section 3.3.1. Coordinates are recorded as lists following the same convention as Table 3.3 and outlined in Section 3.3.1. To simplify the data collection, no reinforcement is considered in these layers, only the geometrical properties.

3.3.1.3. Wall Connections

The *Wall Connections* table describes any internal connections within the wall geometry that were recovered or can be recovered post-deconstruction. For example, in element *G01* in Figure 3.3, two M20 (20 mm diameter) bolt connections are fixed into the upper boundary with an approximate depth of 165 mm. The connections extended above and inserted into voids in the underside of the next wall. The voids were then backfilled with grout or mortar to create the wall-to-wall connection during assembly. Theoretically, even once the connection is cut along the wall boundary during deconstruction, the ungrouted rod component can be removed without damaging the inlaid thread, making the connection reusable. It is assumed that the grout-filled voids will not be cored out post-deconstruction; however, this could also be possible. Therefore, it is helpful to include any existing connections that can be recovered to serve future designs. Another typical example is wall-to-wall starter bars, which follow the same premise as the bolted connections, where the upper component can be removed after deconstruction (illustrated in element *KG03* in Annex A, Figure A1).

Each record in the spreadsheet describes a single connection (no lists) and includes the 3D point location, depth, diameter, and a type description (e.g. bolted, starter bar, etc.). If the diameter of a bar or bolted connection is given as a string (e.g. M20, M24, etc.), convert it into an integer or float when recording the data.

If no recoverable connections exist, inserting a zero into the *Count* attribute will override the Not Null constraints for the other attributes, which can be left empty. Table 3.6 summarises the expected information for the *Wall Connections* table.

Table 3.6. Wall Connections table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Count [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Integer counting the number of recoverable connections.
Location Coordinates [<i>point (x, z, y)</i>]	Not Null	3D point location of each recoverable connection. E.g., G01 has two connections: (200, 3480, 90) and (3384, 3480, 90).
Depth [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Connection depth in mm. Integer or float.
Diameter [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Diameter in mm. Integer or float.
Connection Type [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Description of connection. Recorded in uppercase letters, e.g., BOLTED or STARTER BAR.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

3.3.1.4. Corbel Geometry

Corbels are treated separately from the primary geometry to simplify the shape and reinforcement modelling. The method for mapping corbel geometries is approached generically to improve efficiency within the database. A single table is dedicated to storing corbel information from walls, beams, and columns, which can be found in the central area of Figure 2.2.

The mapping convention follows the same method as outlined in Section 3.3.1. However, since a corbel only typically occupies two planes, one view can be left out for simplicity. The remaining plane is recorded in the *Extruded Plane* column ("XZ", "YZ", or "XY"), for downstream automated extrusion. For example, all necessary points can be captured from the side and plan views in Figure 3.3, so the front view (XZ) can be left empty.

The proposed methodology also flexibly captures recesses and discontinuities in the corbel geometry. For example, element G01 has two 100 mm tapered recesses along its span (Figure 3.3). These are essential aspects to capture parametrically, as they influence the reinforcement design, development lengths, and support lengths for seated floor slabs. The orange markers in Figure 3.3 illustrate the coordinates to be recorded. Table 3.7 summarises the expected information for the *Corbel Geometry* table.

Table 3.7. Corbel Geometry table attributes and description.

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 3.2.
Count [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	An integer for the number of corbels in a given Product ID.
Extruded Plane [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The remaining plane not parametrically described by the coordinates below. Choose from either XZ , YZ , or XY .
Front View Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, z, r)</i>]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the front elevation of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.

Side View Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (y, z, r)]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the cross-sectional view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Plan View Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (x, y, r)]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the plan view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

3.3.2. Wall Longitudinal Reinforcement Design

Spatially defining the reinforcement design is required to revalorise an element in new structural designs. Without understanding the unique reinforcement design in each element, structural analyses cannot be performed, and the only reuse function a reclaimed element may serve is in a downcycled capacity (i.e. the demands in the new structure are less than in the original donor structure). Parameterising the longitudinal reinforcement design poses several challenges, particularly in wall elements. First, the frequency of voids and discontinuities increases the complexity of the design, while designating longitudinal and transverse axes varies with component function. To adaptively capture the reinforcement design in a robust manner that applies to systems with n number of voids, elements are partitioned into **zone** and **layer** reference systems.

A zone is defined as a continuous bounding polygon that extends from one discontinuity or void to the next. Each zone is described by a 2D polygon within its specified *Zone Plane* descriptor, corresponding to the primary cross-sectional view, assuming constant extrusion through the remaining plane. Wall zones can be classified as follows:

- **Base (B):** Horizontal wall zones beneath voids (sills).
- **Header (H):** Horizontal wall zones above voids (lintels).
- **Flank (F):** Vertical flanking zones beside voids (walls).
- **Single (Z):** Uniform geometry without voids or discontinuities.
- **Corbel (_C):** Dedicated zones for corbels, prefixed by primary zone (Fig. 3.4).

Hence, the number of zones within an element depends on the frequency and location of voids. Figure 3.3 represents a single-void system, where a standard double-void system could include a door and a window. Annex A presents examples of geometries with different voids and zones. The sum of all zone areas should encompass the entire element geometry. Figure 3.4 illustrates the zone reference system for element G01.

Once the element geometry has been completely partitioned, reinforcement **layers** within each zone can be defined. A *layer* describes a set of reinforcing bars with constant diameter, spacing, and steel grade within the same plane. Zones and layers follow a few simple rules:

- Zones must encompass the entire length of each reinforcement layer within that zone, with no partial coverage.

- Layers must maintain uniform spacing, diameter, and grade, with any variation requiring a new layer.
- Layer positions are recorded as centre-to-centre measurements.

Therefore, the process of mapping the longitudinal reinforcement design can be summarised into the following steps, using Figures 3.4 and 3.5 as guides:

1. Identify all of the zones within an element and record the polygon coordinates (e.g., $((x_1, z_1), (x_2, z_2))$).
2. Identify the orientation and number of layers within each zone (Figure 3.5).
3. In the first zone, select the first bar in the layer (closest to the origin or axis).
4. Define the start and end points of the bar, resembling a *linestring*.
5. Define the number of bars within the layer, the diameter of the bars, the spacing, and the steel grade.
6. Move on to the next layer within the zone and repeat.
7. Avoid recording duplicates of any layers or bars. Each layer or bar only needs to be recorded once.

When corbels are present, they are given their own zone and necessary reinforcement layers. In Figure 3.5, although the 5 mm longitudinal rebars in the corbels are aligned with identical bars in zone *HI*, the spacing varies, so the corbel reinforcement is given its own layers L1 and L2 (within zone *HIC*). The zone ID given to a corbel zone should start with the same zone name as the overall section it is located in, suffixed by a 'C', then an incrementing integer (Figure 3.4).

Table 3.8 summarises the expected information for the *Wall Long Reinf* table. The concrete cover is separated into the (x, y, z) directions in the event that the cover is not uniform around the section. The construction confidence margin specified in the original drawings is also required. If a wall is *mirrored* in Table 3.3, then there is no need to make a new record of the reinforcement design. Link the mirrored design to the original design via the *Reinf ID*.

There is quite a substantial amount of freedom when it comes to defining the zone and layer reference systems. So long as all steel reinforcement is accounted for within an element with the correct geometrical and spatial properties, then the specific details of how the zones are defined are less critical. Element KG03 illustrates an excellent example of this in Figure A1. Here, the wall has no voids, but due to the irregular profile in the *y* direction, the element could be subdivided into three zones – Flank 1 (F1), Flank 2 (F2), and Flank 3 (F3). The zones would be designated as flanks instead of base zones or headers because the primary load-bearing and bending reinforcement (*longitudinal reinforcement*) is oriented vertically. This approach allows changes in reinforcement sizes and spacings to be captured between the different areas throughout the section. However, the same result could be achieved by using only a single all-encompassing zone, with the necessary spatial information captured in the layer data, since all rebar vertically span the same length from bottom to top. As long as changes in diameter and spacing are captured by creating new

layers wherever necessary, any specific approach using the generic framework proposed will reach the same outcome. The proposed methods simply offer a degree of standardisation to improve the efficiency of the process and downstream modelling applications.

Figure 3.4. Example zoning convention for Prinsenhof façade element G01.

Table 3.8. Wall Long Reinf table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Reinf ID [string]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 3.2.
Zone ID [string]	Not Null	Name given to each zone. E.g. B1 , F1 , F2 , H1 , HC1 . "C" is given to zones representing corbels.
Zone Plane [string]	Not Null	The plane that the polygon extends over. Either XZ , YZ , or XY .
Zone Start [point (h_1, v_1)]	Not Null	Starting zone coordinates (horizontal, vertical).
Zone End [point (h_2, v_2)]	Not Null	Ending zone coordinates (horizontal, vertical).
Layer ID [string]	Not Null	Sequential labelling of each layer, written as L[x] (Fig. 3.5).
Concrete Cover [point (x, z, y)]	Null	Mean concrete cover depth in each direction, in mm.

Concrete Cover Confidence (\pm) [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Construction confidence margin in cover depth specified in the original drawings (e.g. \pm 5 mm).
Layer Start [<i>point</i> (h_1, v_1)]	Not Null	Starting layer position (horizontal, vertical). Taken at the centre of the bar.
Layer End [<i>point</i> (h_2, v_2)]	Not Null	Ending layer position (horizontal, vertical). Taken at the centre of the bar.
Layer Position [<i>point</i>]	Not Null	Centre position of the first bar in the layer relative to the plane not included in <i>Zone Plane</i> (closest to the axis or origin).
Number of Bars [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Number of bars in the layer.
Bar Diameter [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	The diameter of each bar in the layer, in mm.
Bar Spacing [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Centre-to-centre spacing between each bar in the layer (constant).
Steel Grade [<i>string</i>]		Specified steel grade reported in the original design documentation.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

3.3.2.1. Reinforcement Anchorage – Layer and Zone Systems

The anchoring conditions at the end of each rebar and layer are critical for several capacity estimations involving bond development lengths and stress-strain relationships. Ordinarily, hooks of various lengths, shapes, and radii are applied to the rebar ends to anchor them within the concrete. Systems of this variety can be considered **layer anchorage** systems, as they provide anchorage on a per-bar (per-layer) basis. However, hairpin systems (U-shaped bars) are often used as an alternative means of anchoring the reinforcement cage over a **zone**, rather than each bar. Therefore, the ratio of hairpins to layers is not always 1:1 (Figure 3.5), creating discrepancies when recording the data. The data collection templates separate anchorage systems into either *layer* or *zone anchorage*. Table 3.9 summarises the attributes of both types of reinforcement anchorage.

If no end conditions are applied to a bar, leave it empty in the datasheets. In this case, there should be hairpins or some other system providing anchorage to the bars or group. However, in the context of this database, the anchorage attributes only consider the end conditions of each bar or group of bars, not the development lengths based on code guidelines. For this reason, a straight rebar with no hooked conditions (no layer anchoring) and no hairpins (no zone anchoring) can be inserted as NONE in the *Anchorage Type* attribute. For zone anchorage, record properties only once, in the row corresponding to the correct zone in the spreadsheet.

Figure 3.5. Reinforcement design in Prinsenhof element G01. Reinforcement ID = GWAP01.

Table 3.9. Steel Anchorage table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Anchorage Type [string]	Not Null	Description of anchorage type in capital letters. E.g. HOOKED (layer), HAIRPIN (zone), NONE.
Bent Angle (layer) [float]	Not Null	Record the start (left or bottom) and end (right or top) angle of any hook in degrees.
Hooked length (layer) [float]	Not Null	Record the length of a hook at the start (left or bottom) and end (right or top) of a bar. Enter zero if an end is straight.
Bent Angle (zone) [float]	Not Null	Each bent angle in the hairpin. This allows irregular shapes to be captured. Record each angle as a list.
Radius [float]	Not Null	The radius of a bend, if it has curvature, in mm. Enter zero if there is no radius.
Diameter [int]	Not Null	Diameter of hairpins, in mm.
Spacing [int]	Not Null	Spacing between pins as specified in drawings, in mm.
Number of Pins [int]	Not Null	Number of pins within the zone.
Pinned Span [string]	Not Null	The span over which the pins are spaced. Requires X , Y , or Z as input.
Notes [text]	Null	Any additional technical notes. E.g., if hairpins are only on one side or vary on either side of a zone.

3.3.3. Wall Transverse Reinforcement Design

The transverse reinforcement design follows the longitudinal reference system developed earlier. Based on each zone, the shape of the transverse reinforcement is defined by recording a list of each critical point in the bent shape. This is achieved by specifying the 2D plane in which the reinforcement is bent (XZ, YZ, or XY), the angle at each point in the shape, and the coordinates corresponding to the necessary plane. Such an approach allows irregular geometries to be recorded without the need for a shape code typically found in manufacturing standards. This system assumes the transverse reinforcement is not bent in multiple directions and can be described in a 2D plane. If a stirrup has an open end or a transverse rebar has a straight end, enter 0 degrees into the bent angle.

A zone can have more than one entry as long as it's correctly identified, which may be necessary when two parallel straight or bent rebars are placed in the element instead of stirrups. Each rebar layer should be recorded separately to capture any niche details. An example case can be found in element KG03 from the Prinsenhof data and in Figure A1. Table 3.10 summarises the attributes required to map the transverse reinforcement design.

Table 3.10. Wall Transv Reinf table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Reinf ID [string]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 3.2.
Zone ID [string]	Not Null	The identifier given to each zone, matching Table 3.8.
Description [string]	Not Null	Description of transverse reinforcement type. E.g., Closed Stirrup, Open Stirrup, Bent Rebar, Straight Rebar, etc.

Bar Diameter [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Diameter of transverse reinforcement, in mm.
Spacing [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Spacing of reinforcement within the zone, in mm.
Num. Bends [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Number of bends in the reinforcement shape. This value should match the length of the <i>Shape</i> list next.
Bent Plane [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The plane over which the transverse reinforcement is bent (based on the orthographic drawing) – XZ , YZ , or XY .
Shape [<i>list of points</i> (θ, x, z, y)]	Not Null	A list of three points at each bend in the shape. Includes an angle, θ , and the coordinates matching the <i>Bent Plane</i> entered above – i.e. one axis will be left empty.
Span Axis [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The span over which the transverse reinforcement is spaced, i.e. whatever axis is not included in the <i>Bent Plane</i> – X , Y , or Z .
Span Position [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The start and end points of the reinforced span.
Steel Grade [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Specified steel grade reported in the original design documentation.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

3. 4. Beams

The data collection of beam elements conceptually follows the same mapping conventions and reference systems as the wall elements discussed throughout Section 3.3. In general, the process for collecting beam data involves:

1. Mapping the geometry in a 2D orthographic format.
2. Mapping the longitudinal steel design by defining the zone and layer reference systems.
3. Mapping the transverse reinforcement design by defining the shape of the bars within each zone.

By implementing zones, irregular cross-sections can be partitioned and simplified, enabling the reinforcement design to be more easily defined. The attributes used to describe steps 1 to 3 above are the same as those used for walls. The only distinguishing differences are:

- The *Void* table has been removed.
- The *Additional Panelling* table has been removed.
- The *zone naming convention* has changed. For beams, zones are designated as either **flange (F)** zones, **web (W)** zones, or a **single zone (Z)** for uniform sections.

Figure 3.6 provides examples of beam elements and their possible zoning, along with the new naming convention. Remember that as long as the rules outlined in Section 3.3.2 are followed, the selected zones can vary based on the user’s preference. However, half-joints in beams (Figure 3.6) are classified as part of the global geometry, not corbels, so the data should be structured accordingly.

Figure 3.6. Zone allocation for different beam types.

3. 5. Columns

Data collection for column elements follows the same concepts and methodologies discussed in Section 3.3 for walls. Like beams, the process begins with mapping the geometry, longitudinal reinforcement design, and transverse reinforcement design. The primary differences between the walls and columns are:

- The *Void* table has been removed.
- The *Additional Panelling* table has been removed.
- Elliptical and curved cross-sections are considered.

Two primary cross-sectional types can be defined for columns: *elliptical* and *rectangular* cross-sections. An ellipse is described as being made of entirely tangential coordinates. A tangent line is drawn between two infinitely close points on a plane curve, resembling a line parallel to the curved surface. Hence, a tangent line cannot be drawn relative to a straight edge, where the distance between two parallel points is no longer infinitesimally small. If the intersection of the tangents from four points of contraflexure along a curved surface creates a bounding rectangle, then the section is considered elliptical. If a curved section includes straight portions, then it is regarded as a rectangular section with curved edges. Circular sections are elliptical sections with a constant diameter. Similarly, square sections are rectangular sections of constant width. For the *Cross-Section* attribute in the *Column Geometry* table, record either **Elliptical** or **Rectangular**.

Ellipse Coordinates

Curved Rectangular Section

Figure 3.7. Geometric coordinates of elliptical and curved rectangular column sections.

The mapping convention introduced in Section 3.3.1 adequately captures both scenarios using the *Radius* attribute. The path of an ellipse can be described by the coordinates of four points that produce tangent lines parallel to the local axes. The radius of each point to the local origin then describes the curvature, as shown in Figure 3.7. For a rectangular section with curved edges, specifying the relevant radius of the curvature at each recorded point sufficiently describes the overall shape (Figure 3.7). Recording a radius of 0 indicates that no curvature is present, and the point represents an abrupt change in direction (corner).

For the transverse reinforcement in columns – rectangular ties, circular spirals and hoop sections are now included. For circular reinforcement, define the *Shape* attribute in the same way as described in Section 3.3.2, using the elliptical definitions provided above and substituting the **Radius** at each point in place of the **Bent Angle** attribute. Figure 3.8 provides examples of common column types and how they can be subdivided into zones. Column zones follow the same naming convention as beams described in Section 3.4 (flange, web, single).

Figure 3.8. Zone allocation for different column types.

3. 6. Slabs

3.6.1. Solid Slabs

Solid floor slabs follow the same conventions as walls described in Section 3.3. Slab geometry is much simpler than walls, making the definitions of geometrical zones and reinforcement layers likewise easier. The only noteworthy distinction here is that, unlike beams and columns, voids are again considered due to the possibility of inlaid voids for ducting, plumbing, HRV, and other strategic recesses. Otherwise, the approach for mapping the geometry, longitudinal reinforcement design, and transverse reinforcement design is described in Sections 3.3.1, 3.3.2, and 3.3.3.

3.6.2. Hollow-core Slabs (HCS)

Prestressed hollow-core floors are a highly standardised slab design that can be parameterised in a more straightforward format than was necessary for the earlier element types. The general geometric and void properties, connections, structural topping details, and prestressing information are outlined in the following sections.

3.6.2.1. HCS Geometry

The geometry of an HCS can be directly characterised by physical dimensions instead of a spatial system. Table 3.11 summarises the attributes required to describe a hollow-core slab. Figure 3.9 provides a visual aid for deriving the characteristics in Table 3.11.

Table 3.11. HCS Geometry table attribute and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [string]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 3.2.
Reinf ID [string]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 3.2.
Count [integer]	Not Null	Number of elements with identical geometry [Product ID].
Height [int]	Not Null	Cross-sectional height, in mm.
Length [int]	Not Null	Floor slab length, in mm.
Width [int]	Not Null	Cross-sectional width, in mm.
Void Count [int]	Not Null	Number of cores in the slab.
Void Diameter [float]	Not Null	Core diameter in the horizontal and vertical directions (Figure 3.9).
Concrete Cover [float]	Not Null	Concrete cover depth to the bottom and top of the cores, in mm.
External Web Thickness [float]	Not Null	Thickness of the outer web between the slab edge and outer core, in mm.
Concrete Strength Class [string]	Not Null	Concrete class based on original design specifications.
Density [float]	Null	Known or approximated concrete density in kg/m ³ .
Max Aggregate Size [int]	Null	Maximum aggregate used in concrete mixture (optional).
Notes [text]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

Figure 3.9. Typical hollow-core floor section from Prinsenhof A office complex.

3.6.2.2. HCS Connections

The connections considered in HCS floor systems include:

- Shear connections between slabs and walls (located along the outer edge) and their position in mm.
- Longitudinal connections between slabs and walls (located at slab ends) and their position in mm.
- Shear connections between adjacent slabs (located along the inner edge) and their position in mm.

When a floor system is deconstructed, the connections between adjacent elements are sawn through. If the connections are left in the slab, designers need to know that this area is compromised and cannot be used for future connections. Likewise, if the connection is removed, the void left in its place will likely be backfilled and cannot be used in future connections. For simplification, only the function and position of the connection are recorded. Designers can refer to the original drawings for specific details. If no connections are present, enter 0 in the data field.

3.6.2.3. Structural Topping

For reuse purposes, knowledge about whether the structural topping layer is still attached to the slab is also necessary. Since the topping will have been sawn down the longitudinal edge of the slab during deconstruction, the diaphragm action it supplied can no longer be achieved. However, it is often left in place due to the significant difficulty of effectively removing the topping without damaging the slab. The topping will affect both structural and architectural design phases for reuse, so it needs to be accounted for in the database. Table 3.12 summarises the attributes required for the structural topping.

Table 3.12. Structural Topping table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Present? [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	True or False Boolean identifying if a structural topping is still in place.
Thickness [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Thickness of structural topping, in mm.
Mesh Diameter [<i>int</i>]	Null	Diameter of the steel mesh reinforcement inside the slab, in mm (optional).
Mesh Spacing [<i>int</i>]	Null	Grid spacing (assumed uniform) of the steel mesh reinforcement inside the slab, in mm (optional).

3.6.2.4. HCS Prestressing

Prestressing information in HCS systems is critical for determining the slab's load-bearing capacities. Table 3.13 summarises the attributes required for the prestressing design in hollow-core floor slabs. The *prestressing layer* describes all strands along the same

horizontal x-axis position. The *Layer Number*, therefore, represents the relative position of the layer, starting at the base and incrementing vertically.

Table 3.13. HCS Prestressing table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Reinf ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 3.2.
Strand ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique ID for each prestressing strand in an element. Serves as the primary key in the MySQL RDBMS.
Layer Number [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	The prestressing layer number, starting from the slab base.
Strand Coordinates [<i>point (x,y)</i>]	Not Null	The cross-sectional position of each prestressing strand.
Number of Wires [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	The number of wires used in each tendon, e.g. 1-wire, 3-wire, or 7-wire strand, etc.
Strand Diameter [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Diameter of the prestressed tendon in mm.
Strand Grade	Null	Steel grade designation for the prestressed tendon.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be of use to future designers.

3. 7. Material Properties

The material specifications from historical national standards are stored in a collective library within the database. The database is structured so that only the concrete strength class or steel grades are required for input in Tables 3.3, 3.8, 3.10, and 3.13. The class or grade specifications are then linked to the properties library via an FK relationship. Manufacturing standards from the 20th and 21st centuries have been collected and stored from each country, including the modern Eurocode provisions.

Material properties from standards dating back to 1918 for reinforcing steel and 1918 for concrete have been collected from each ReCreate partner country. The characteristics of interest can be found in the grey tables in Figure 2.2. This work is ongoing, and to further build and improve the libraries, it would be beneficial for each country cluster to review its archives and incorporate information from its respective country codes into the libraries. The material libraries are publicly available at the following Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16809569>.

3. 8. Using the Excel Templates

Data collection is managed through Microsoft Excel templates prepared in the format reflecting the information in Tables 3.1 to 3.13. The data is recorded manually for each element within a deconstruction project. Explanations of the required attributes are presented throughout Section 3. For guidance on the expected formatting of the data while moving through the process, refer to the datatypes specified in Figure 2.2. To check whether a field is optional or mandatory, refer to the constraints outlined in the relevant table from

Table 3.1 to 3.13 – *Null* means that the attribute is optional, and *Not Null* indicates that it is a mandatory parameter.

Do not reorganise attributes within the spreadsheets or change the layout of templates. The storage algorithms developed for MySQL are hard-coded to the spreadsheet layout.

Annex B provides checklists for the different phases of the data collection stage. Table B1 presents a *pre-collection* checklist outlining the most important resources to have ready before starting data collection. Table B2 provides a checklist outlining the process for collecting the data from each element in the inventory. Table B3 outlines the final cleaning steps to take after completing data collection, ensuring the Excel sheets are free from errors and incorrect formatting.

4. Final Remarks

For the design of new buildings and structures that incorporate reclaimed elements, it is necessary to have a database available from which these elements can be accessed. The task of creating an open database for precast concrete components in the EU is covered within WP1. This report outlines an early-stage framework for the data collection process and the methodologies developed to define reclaimed elements parametrically. The purpose of the data collection stage is to parametrically describe the geometric, longitudinal, and transverse reinforcement designs of a precast element, such that it can be redeveloped into a digital twin or BIM model capable of performing detailed structural analyses. The approach for reverse engineering structural precast elements into a set of parameters is discussed in detail throughout this report. The relational database is created and hosted within MySQL, an open-source relational database management system application. The database also serves as a valuable platform to define architectural and life-cycle characteristics to provide a holistic overview of each reclaimed element.

The data from over 1,100 elements of all types have been successfully collected from each partner country and stored within the database using the systems introduced in this report. A complete and detailed account of the relational database architecture can be found in the accompanying scientific article, which will be linked after peer review.

If any readers are interested in learning more about the element database and its ongoing progress, or have any feedback, queries, or concerns, please get in touch with bj.matthews114@gmail.com.

5. References

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- Hernández Vargas, J., Stenberg, E. & Kotkavuo, N (2025). A taxonomy for urban mining of precast concrete. The ReCreate project.
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Annex A

Additional Wall Examples

Figure A1. Prinsenhof A facade element KG03 design.

Figure A2. Prinsenhof A facade elements G07 and G10 with zone allocation.

Annex B

Data Collection Checklists

Table B1. Pre-collection preparation checklist.

	Item/Action	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element inventory	Collect an inventory identifying all structural precast elements that were reclaimed from deconstruction.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Floor Plan drawings	Collect all available floor plan drawings from the archives for metadata and taxonomies.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Construction drawings	Cross-sectional designs of elements, including geometrical and reinforcement detailing.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Inspection data	Compile any available on-site inspection information that might be used to update original specifications.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element Photos	Collect any photos taken before or during deconstruction to link to the element in the database.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data Collection templates	Prepare all of the data collection spreadsheets needed based on the available element types from the deconstruction project.

Table B2. Data collection process checklist.

	Item/Action	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Donor building metadata	Fill in the metadata information for the donor building. Each project should be a single record in the spreadsheet.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element metadata	Fill in the metadata information for all elements by element type. Every element within the deconstruction inventory should have one record in the spreadsheet.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element geometry	Map the geometry for all unique elements using the information in Section 3.3.1. Start with the global geometry coordinates, then the void coordinates (for walls and slabs), connection details, and corbel details (walls, beams, and columns).
<input type="checkbox"/>	Additional panels	For walls, if additional non-load-bearing layers are kept intact, map the geometry using the same conventions as above in a separate table (sheet), linking the information with the element's product ID.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Longitudinal reinforcement design	Map the longitudinal reinforcement design using the systems developed in Section 3.3.2. Only record each unique design once, linking the Product ID with the Reinforcement ID. Fill in the anchorage details for each layer or zone based on the available drawings and information. Note that all layer coordinates are taken centre-to-centre.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Transverse reinforcement design	Map the transverse reinforcement design using the same reference systems (zones) as the longitudinal design and the systems developed in Section 3.3.3.

Table B3. Post-collection checklist.

	Item/Action	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check data types	Check that the data types used for each attribute match those specified in Figure 2.2 and Tables 3.1 to 3.13. Use the definitions in Section 2.1 if anything is unclear.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check null/not null constraints	Check that no mandatory data has been missed throughout the spreadsheets. Fields left incorrectly empty will stop the data from being stored within the RDBMS. Refer to the relevant tables (Table 3.1 to 3.13) to view the necessary constraints.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check for required uniqueness	Several IDs must be unique to satisfy the key constraints in the database management system. Check the requirements stipulated throughout Section 3 and make sure all taxonomies meet the necessary guidelines.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check running numbers	Often in Excel, when clicking and dragging repeated values through multiple cells, numbers can incrementally increase, leading to errors in the data. Check that no running numbers have been let loose throughout the spreadsheets.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Linked resources	Ensure that all necessary drawings and/or photos are linked alongside the data in the RDBMS and are supplied with appropriate and clear naming.